

Erratum to: Service-oriented middleware for the Future Internet: state of the art and research directions

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The original version of this article unfortunately contained a mistake in the authorship. The spelling of Panos Vassiliadis' name was incorrect. The correct spelling is Panos Vassiliadis.

The online version of the original article can be found under
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